

TEACHING AND METHODS OF COLOR AND PENCIL DRAWING IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Annotation

Pen is the basis of all forms of fine art. Since the 18th century, "pencil drawing" has been a term used to describe the creation of an image using lines, and introduces important features that define the shape, size, structure, and character of an object in all forms of art.

The basis of fine arts is pencil drawing. For a more in-depth study of the features of pen drawing, there are several types of conditional descriptions.

Keywords: Fine arts, differentiated education, methodology, method, creative process, educational technology, pedagogical technology, Individual education, art education, pencil drawing, Ordinary black pencils, graphite mining , spatial state, N.Kante, etude, sketch, engraving, inogravure, lithography.

Introduction

Today, our country, personally President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, is carrying out a number of practical reforms to reform the system of continuing education, to improve it on the basis of world experience. In particular, it is important to work on the development of secondary schools, which are the main link in the system of continuing education.

Differentiated education is one of the most effective types of modern pedagogical technologies in increasing the effectiveness of fine arts lessons in schools.

When thinking about differentiated education, it is important to have a clear idea of its pros and cons. When it comes to the benefits of differentiated learning, the following should be noted.

- ✓ All students in the class will be able to master the program materials.
- ✓ All students in the class will have an increase in knowledge and skills, creative work, which will increase students' interest in science.
- ✓ All students in the class become more active. Because every child in the lower

✓ learning group tries to move to the higher learning group. Children in the upper learning group try not to fall into the lower learning group.

✓ As students are given knowledge according to their abilities and capabilities, there is no pressure on them to master the workload.

✓ The needs of gifted students in the classroom for in-depth and comprehensive knowledge are also met.

✓ Differentiated education helps to democratize and humanize it.

Differentiated education contributes to the dynamic development of the knowledge and skills of all 'students' in the classroom by providing students with individual, professional development, proper and competent organization of their legitimate independent work.

In doing so, the teacher is able to carry out the lessons by conducting each learning process, conducting, organizing, conducting. Due to the diversity of factors, support for science, technique and aesthetics of all students in the class, the knowledge imparted and the methodology developed on this basis do not affect all students equally.

Physically, students do not assimilate learning materials in the same way. It is important to note that this can be used to educate children. One effective way is a differentiated approach to education. In the works of some educators there is an in-depth analysis of the scientific basis of differentiated education, its scientific basis, the experience of individual work with students.

In pedagogical theory, pedagogical scholars regulate two types of stratified education:

1. Level stratification.
2. Specialized stratification.

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There are two types of hierarchies:

1. Individual education. Individual work is done with each student according to their abilities and capabilities.
2. Group education. Students are divided into two or more groups according to their abilities and capabilities.

Specialized stratification, on the other hand, focuses on the in-depth study of a subject, its orientation to different professions, or its mastery of the basics. These include schools (classes), faculties, and clubs that provide in-depth study of the fine arts.

In the theory and practice of education, there are the following types of education, differentiated from the fine arts:

- Differentiated schools;
- Stratified classes;
- Stratified groups;

- Individualized education.

These majors can be both advanced and specialized. For many years, there have been schools and classes specializing in fine arts, as well as elective courses, among other disciplines in pedagogical practice. Many experts agree that teaching students in groups of low-achieving children (low, medium, high) can lead to negative consequences for the activities of high-achieving and low-achieving children.

In particular, they note that high-achieving children are characterized by arrogance, self-esteem or disregard for others, overestimation, and rudeness. At the same time, this category of children has a fear story.

This is because they may also fall from the upper group to the lower group as a result of not completing the tasks at a high level. Low-achieving students, on the other hand, feel discriminated against and uneducated in stratified groups.

Often, peers, siblings, and parents feel like mentally retarded children. As a result, they become depressed and lose interest in reading. They become people who don't join their classmates and don't interfere with their children. Gradually, this category of students may be negatively affected by various reprimands and insults from teachers, parents, and classmates.

As a result, they become indifferent to everything, everything, and stop developing. As a teacher begins to implement differentiated learning, he or she will need to approach both the pros and cons of the above.

Given these subtleties of the issue, when dividing children into groups, it is advisable to use the simple, first, second, and third groups instead of the words capable, incompetent, assimilating, unassuming, high, and low in the classroom.

It is important to note that differentiated learning is not only effective, but also has its complexities. Its complexity is due to the fact that the teacher teaches on the basis of three different levels of programs. To do this, each group will need separate textbooks, methodologies, didactic and handouts, technical aids from the visual arts, without which it is impossible to organize classes at the required level.

This is reflected in the following directions:

1. Thorough knowledge of the scientific basis of differentiated fine arts education.
2. Be equipped with the necessary training materials for the training.
3. Have a special room and facilities for training.
4. The teacher should be fully aware of the level of knowledge and skills of students in their subject, etc. One of the most difficult and complex aspects of the problem is that the teacher has a complete picture of the students.

It is well-known that each person has his own world, and his knowledge of fine arts is different. And for some as a baby gets older, he or she will outgrow this.

In order to get to know the children in all respects, it is necessary for the teacher to make a pedagogical and psychological diagnosis among the children. This work is directly related to: the general ability of the student, his character, what science he is interested in and to what extent he knows them, interest in reading, level of imagination, thinking and creative thinking, activity and imagination, memory and observation, attention, initiative, independence, conditions for homework, etc. It is also helpful to know the students' health and physiological growth at the time of diagnosis. In conclusion, it should be noted that the teacher should also know the characteristics of the student in the field of fine arts.

In this regard, the teacher should be aware of the development of knowledge and skills of each child in the classroom. It is also important to provide students with knowledge based on their level of knowledge and skills, which will allow them to move students from one group to another when needed.

The pencil draws lines and colors according to the means of illustration. The line drawing is usually light, light and generalized. Through the lines an artistic image is created, tables, conditional drawings, images are made on the class board. Color images accurately describe the size, brightness, materiality, and spatial relationships of an object in the environment. This type of painting is called light-shade and color. Some things are unique in their appearance. Therefore, when depicting such views, a simple type of color image is sometimes chosen - this is called a silhouette - an image that is overlaid with the same flat color line. Depending on the method of drawing, the pen is divided into original and printed types. An original painting is the only example created by an artist with his own hands. Bosmal is a pattern on a piece of paper and is called a stamp. There are several types of stamps; engraving, inogravure, lithography. The pen is divided into academic and creative images, depending on the format. An academic pen is a drawing that is done over a long period of time to learn different shapes and symbols and to master the techniques of drawing. A creative image is an artist's thought, a feeling, and a work of fine art that figuratively expresses his worldview. Drawings, sketches, sketches are widely used in educational and creative work. A draft is a short-term image.

A thorough study of an image of an object or its parts is done through an etude. In sketches and drafts, the real material that is collected and studied in depth is called the sketch, which is the first sketch that is intended to be used during the creation of a creative painting or work.

As you know, observation is the ability to determine the shape, color, structure, size, and proportions of an object, its spatial position, and so on. The meaningful image of an object is formed on the basis of feeling in our mind.

At the heart of this image are the possibilities of expressing what is being observed with the foundations of the external sign. One of the hallmarks of observation is learning, knowing, and understanding. Observation is directly related to people's ability to see. When drawing, the artist carefully studies and analyzes nature.

It tries to determine the characteristics of its structure, and it is called synthesis, which expresses the idea of the structure of the object, the interdependence of its parts, the spatial state as a whole. So, the process of drawing an object consists of observing, analyzing and describing it in detail. To accurately and convincingly depict an object, one must learn to observe the universe. As well as teaching writing and reading, a person who practices regularly with perseverance and endurance can learn to draw correctly.

There are many types of black pencils available today. There are many types of pencils, from medium to soft. These are; "T", "2T", "N", "2N", "M", "2M", "3M" or V, T, 2T, M, 2M, N, 2N, NV, V, 2V and so on.

If we look at our history, in the primitive times, people created various images in caves, mountains and rocks. They carved the walls of the caves with something harder and made different shapes. But in the process of development, various tools in imaging have improved. Ordinary black pencils are one of them.

In the 16th century, when graphite sticks were used in painting in England, they were found to be able to draw very elegant and beautiful lines on the surface of paper. Today's black pencils were invented in the late 17th century by the French scientist N. Kante, who suggested that the pen be glued to a wooden device. Pencils marked with the letter "T" mean "hard". Plaster sockets with such pencils are used to draw. The letter "M" means "soft" and is used to make sketches or sketches of compositions.

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